

Building Sustainable Collaboration Through Effective Leadership Sustainability Mediated by Innovation Capability and Moderated by External Stakeholder Interest: Case Study in Indonesia Social Security Administration Agency

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze several issues, including analyzing the relationship between Effective leadership sustainability and Innovation Capability; Effective leadership sustainability towards Collaborative Sustainability Performance; Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance; and Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance and External Stakeholder Interest. The sampling technique used in this study was through a census to provide equal opportunities to all BPJS Kesehatan branches as the research population as well as the sample. BPJS Kesehatan has deputy regional offices which are divided into 13 regions consisting of 126 branch offices (one branch office is administrative) and 388 district/city offices. For the purposes of data analysis, this study used Partial least squares (SmartPLS) path modeling, SPSS, and Nvivo software. The study concluded that the answers to research questions related to research objectives, both those related to scientific interests and problem solving, were in accordance with the results of theoretical studies and testing of research results. Some of the findings of this study include Effective Sustainable Leadership has a direct effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance, and Innovation Capability moderated by External Stakeholder Interests has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance.

Keywords: *Sustainable Collaboration, Effective Leadership Sustainability, Innovation Capability, External Stakeholder Interest, Social Security, National Health Insurance.*

INTRODUCTION

Excellent health services are a community need and are often a measure of the success of development (Rumengan et al., 2015). Therefore, at present, public health insurance is an essential program for most countries. The health insurance program is a national program with the principles of social insurance, equity, and a cooperation system (Kemenkes, 2014).

The level of public health is very influential on the level of community welfare because the level of health has a close relationship with the level of poverty. Meanwhile, the level of poverty will be related to the level of welfare. The relationship between health levels and poverty can be said to be the vicious circle of poverty. In the concept of poverty, there are three main points that cause a person to become poor, including low levels of health, low incomes, and low levels of education (Widiastuti, 2017).

Therefore, referring to Law no. 40 of 2004, the government decided by creating a National Health Insurance (JKN) program organized by the Social Security Administration Agency (BPJS). One of the objectives of this program is to guarantee the right of everyone to obtain access to safe, quality, and affordable health services.

BPJS Kesehatan has the authority to establish cooperation with health facilities, including hospitals. Private hospitals are not required to be providers, while government hospitals are mandatory. Cooperation and contract extensions are carried out with certain conditions, based on the assessment of BPJS Kesehatan. Every year the contract is renewed and can be extended if it still meets the requirements and the agreement of both parties.

Since it was implemented on January 1, 2014, BPJS Kesehatan participants have reached 133.4 million people or 53 percent of Indonesia's population. After five years, in 2019 the number of BPJS Health participants has increased by 224,149,019 people or 83% of the Indonesian population. Along with the increase in the number of participants, the number of utilizations of health services also increased from 92.3 million in 2014 to 223.4 million in 2017. This indicates that the existence of the JKN-KIS program makes health services more accessible and the public is more aware about

importance of using health services. In addition, in 2016, the contribution of the JKN-KIS program to the Indonesian economy is estimated at Rp. 152.2 trillion, creating employment by 1.45 million people, and increasing life expectancy by 2.9 years.

However, since the beginning of its implementation, the JKN program has continued to experience a deficit. In fact, the deficit is predicted to reach IDR 28 trillion by the end of 2019. According to BPJS Kesehatan, the deficit is caused by the high number of people suffering from chronic diseases so that the cost of health services increases (Putri, 2021). If this deficit problem is not addressed immediately, it will have an impact on the decline in the quality of health services, the trust of service providers and service users so that the welfare of the community will decrease. If the deficit problem is not immediately addressed, then UHC will be difficult to achieve (Aidha & Chrisnahutama, 2020).

Some observers argue that the problem with BPJS is not only in budget management but is also related to the management of resources at the institution. In achieving its organizational goals, BPJS is required to be able to cooperate with various relevant stakeholders. To build a collaboration that involves the government, the private sector and the community, collaboration is needed. However, this is still a problem in Latin American and African countries and low-middle income countries (Odorico et al., 2014; Olu et al., 2019; Ota et al., 2018; Glandon et al., 2018). The complexity of the relationship with hospitals in setting rates, for example, is still an annual routine problem experienced by the Organizing Agency in South Korea (NHIS). Likewise, in efforts to build public participation, this is still an obstacle (Service, 2019; Lee, et al, 2019; Oh, Ko et al, 2015).

In addition, the implementation of community-based insurance also requires community support (Akuoko, 2014; Mladovsky et al., 2015). On the other hand, in an effort to achieve the sustainability of the UHC program, policies that are in line with the values of health services are also needed. Inappropriate policies can undermine the value of health services (Erniaty & Harun, 2020). As for program implementing organizations, the management and competence of internal resources and appropriate organizational culture are also important factors (Coutinho et al., 2018; Heine et al., 2016; Passchier, 2017).

As a public institution that involves many actors, collaboration is a way to achieve sustainability. Stakeholder support needs to be harmonized through supportive values; however, it is not clear what values are able to encourage the creation of sustainable collaboration that provides the results as intended by the organization, even in areas where conditions are slower, and cause stakeholder dissatisfaction or referred to as collaborative inertia.

In the perspective of collaboration theory, it takes stages and good governance (collaborative governance) in building a successful collaboration. Collaborative governance as a collaborative process is an important factor in achieving the outcome, namely collaborative sustainability.

This research will fill the gap, how to achieve collaborative sustainability performance as an inseparable part between collaboration and sustainability. Therefore, this study aims to analyze several issues, including analyzing the relationship between Effective leadership sustainability and Innovation Capability; Effective leadership sustainability towards Collaborative Sustainability Performance; Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance; and Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance and External Stakeholder Interest.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Effective Leadership Sustainability and Innovation Capability

Empirical research shows that there are important factors that must be owned and carried out by a leader so that the goals of sustainability can be achieved. The leader's view of the environment has an important role in the conditions that require solutions, making policies, implementing procedures and distributing them to related parties in an effort to achieve sustainability. In the role as a consultant, the leader also monitors and evaluates the development of employee capabilities and organizational targets (Opoku et al., 2015). Leaders also exert influence in efforts to build stakeholder trust through involvement in building organizational governance in order to gain stakeholder support in the long term (Bryson et al., 2020; Cain et al., 2020; Pucher et al., 2017).

As an individual, a leader is involved in managing time effectively, behaving ethically, building innovation and trust among employees, managing change and managing uncertainty as a gradual process, as well as building human resources and building engagement with stakeholders as a commitment (Woloschuk & Raymond, 2010; Tabassi, 2018).

Innovation strategy is a factor that influences collaboration to achieve sustainability. Innovation capability is an "operational capability" that affects collaboration (Chi et al., 2018). In managing complex conditions, managers try to solve various ideas including through innovation. However, the efforts built by managers through innovation oriented towards sustainability still require accountability and attention to the interests of customers (Keskin et al., 2012; Weber &

Khademian, 2008). Innovation can run effectively when it involves/collaborates with external parties on a regular basis (Pongsathornwiwat et al., 2019).

Several previous studies, attributive-based leadership showed a direct influence on innovation capability (Liu & Yang, 2019; Flores et al., 2018; Domínguez et al., 2019). Leaders have an effect on organizational capabilities, namely by increasing the capacity to innovate (Gil et al., 2018). Leading positions in field research do not mention specific style advantages that impact innovation. Leaders in positions as mediators or antecedents have an influence on efforts to innovate, and play a role in creating trust among employees as an effort to create knowledge sharing (Lei et al., 2019).

H₁: There is a direct positive effect between effective leadership sustainability on Innovation Capability

Effective Leadership Sustainability and Collaborative Sustainability Performance

Conceptually, effective leadership in sustainability is a leader who runs the principle starting from oneself (Ulrich & Smallwood, 2015). The results of other studies show that the leadership role shows an influence on the achievement of sustainable social performance (Wang et al., 2014; Opoku et al., 2015; Woloschuk & Raymond, 2010; Lengnick & Hall, 2011; Gupta, 2018; Liu & Yang, 2019; Flores, et al 2018; Jay Joseph, 2018). Meanwhile, in terms of building collaboration, leaders have a role in achieving sustainable collaboration through the implementation of good governance (Liu & Yang, 2019).

From an employee perspective, the social dimensions of sustainability include: participation, cooperation, development, equality of opportunity, health and safety and external relations (Staniškienė & Stankevičiūtė, 2018). Meanwhile, in the perspective of the social community, it is more likely to be translated as a form of survival and happiness for individuals in a group or as a minimum limit that must be met for vulnerable groups (Brown et al., 1987). In the perspective of the UHC program, sustainability is not only related to the aspect of financial adequacy (Okungu & McIntyre, 2019), it is also an agenda to maintain the sustainability of the policies that have been decided (Naimoli et al., 2018), as ethics and values that are adhered to in running the health system, providing access and protection for the community from difficulties due to health costs, especially for vulnerable groups (Mulyanto et al., 2019; Erlangga et al. 2019).

Collaboration needs clarity, commitment, stakeholder management of external interests that may not be aligned. Adaptability and flexibility are also required (Allen et al., 2017; Ansell & Gash, 2008; Butcher et al., 2019; Chakkol et al., 2018; C. H. and S. Vangen, 2005). On the other hand, collaboration is strongly influenced by the role of leadership through knowledge and skills in building collaboration (Adams, 2012). The role of leaders through good management of innovation capability shows an influence on the sustainability of collaboration (Sergeeva & Ali, 2020; Reypens et al., 2021).

H₂: There is a positive effect of effective leadership sustainability on collaborative sustainability performance

Innovation Capability and Collaborative Sustainability Performance

Managers have a role in building organizations to develop innovation capabilities (Rodriguez & Wiengarten, 2017). Innovation has an influence on the three pillars of sustainability performance, especially in the human/social aspect in different ways (Gallagher et al., 2018), also simultaneously with the company's products (León-Bravo et al., 2019).

Information (sharing) from external parties and customers obtained in the value co-creation process can also increase the company's innovation capability (Hung Nguyen, 2018). Other research shows that collaboration involving "public-private" requires increased innovation (Carbonara et al., 2018).

Many studies have shown that the involvement of multiple actors requires collaboration. However, collaboration faces various obstacles and there are still various points of view. Collaboration also means co-action, not individualistic. Collaboration is the path to sustainability (Hrelja et al., 2016; Lozano, 2007). Conceptually, sustainability is still abstract and ambiguous (Lozano, 2008; Owens & Legere, 2015).

The concept of sustainability is related to sustainability development which has its roots in the WCED meeting, 1987, point 27, that "Humanity has the ability to make sustainable development to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". The concept still raises various views, but basically focuses more on the human aspect (Vallance et al., 2011). It is further translated as efforts made to pay attention to aspects of people, planet, and profit (Elkington, 2013).

The research shows that innovation capability is positively related to sustainable performance. Innovation has a direct influence on sustainable performance (Gallagher et al., 2018; Rodriguez, 2016; León, 2019). Innovation in the health system is not an easy thing to do considering the many parties involved and various considerations in the medical aspect. Meanwhile, there is a customer role that needs to be considered in an innovation (Keskin et al., 2012) because stakeholder

support is an important factor that influences collaboration sustainability (Pucher et al., 2017). Collaborating requires innovation including regular involvement of external parties (Carbonara et al., 2018; Pongsathornwivat et al., 2019).

H₃: There is a direct positive effect of innovation capability on collaborative sustainability performance.

Innovation Capability, Collaborative Sustainability Performance, and External Stakeholder Interest

The innovation capabilities of companies are very diverse, influenced by many factors (Saunila et al., 2013). To build innovation, leadership, individual and team aspects are needed as well as other supporting components such as HR development policies, innovation climate and organizational structure configuration (Tuzovic et al., 2018).

The leadership aspect also affects the organization's ability to increase the capacity to innovate (Gil et al., 2018). Leading positions in field research do not mention specific style advantages that impact innovation. Likewise, the position as a mediator or antecedent is related to efforts to innovate, but the leader plays a very important role in creating trust among employees as an effort to create knowledge sharing (Lei et al., 2019).

In complex social environments, managing stakeholder interests can be very challenging (Dew & Sarasvathy, 2007; Pinelli & Maiolini, 2017). Similarly, in developing a shared value as the basis for developing innovation (Fleuren, Wiefferink, & Paulussen, 2004). Interests can differ between internal and external stakeholders (Kangas, 2019). However, the diversity of stakeholder interests cannot be viewed as merely differences but also in terms of common interests, such as: the desire to join forces through value creation for and with stakeholders (Freeman et al, 2010; Kujala, Lehtimäki, & Freeman, 2019).

Interest is inherent in an individual or group that is manifested in actions to get benefits from an object for individuals or groups so that the achievement of interest is a form / method of resolving internal conflicts of interest that are in line with certain administrative patterns or patterns of relationships. Interests that are not in line with common welfare principles must be avoided so as not to cause damage (Krott, 2005). Meanwhile, in another view, stakeholder interests contain intrinsic value and other values that are related or not to the interests of the company, but there is an obligation for the company to manage in a certain pattern (Amadi et al., 2019; Freeman et al., 2010; Thomas Donaldson). and Lee, 1995).

Innovations that are built by taking into account social conditions and aspects of balance with the interests of external stakeholders have a positive influence in building cooperation as the goal of achieving sustainable performance (Herzlinger, 2006; Duygu, 2010). Attention to Innovation Capability is carried out through joint efforts by taking into account the interest of external parties in achieving sustainability performance (Keskin et al., 2013). In the cooperation that is built between "public-private" parties, it is very necessary to strengthen innovation. This encourages the need to pay attention to what interests have an impact on strengthening innovation.

H₄: There is a positive effect of Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance when the interest of External stakeholder interest.

METHODS

Survey development

The questionnaire consists of open and closed questions. The pre-test was conducted using a prepared questionnaire. Based on the results of the analysis, the questionnaire was revised as needed to be used as a follow-up to the research questionnaire. The results of the analysis used the data in accordance with the adjusted questionnaire.

The pre-test is carried out through a questionnaire that has been prepared to be filled in/answered by the head of the branch. From 126 branch heads, 25-30 were selected as representatives representing the three classes of branch heads. The results were analyzed with SPSS and for further adjustment of questions or variables. Furthermore, the questionnaire was distributed back to the head of the branch who had not filled out. All answers that have been adjusted will be further analyzed. For the purposes of data analysis, this study used Partial least squares (SmartPLS) path modeling, SPSS, and Nvivo software.

Variable operation

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Scale
Collaborative sustainability performance	Employee perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee participation • Equal opportunity 	Ordinal
	Community perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity of access • Financial protection 	Ordinal
	Institutional perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community support • Relational 	Ordinal

Effective leadership sustainability	Controlling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrator function • Goal setting Control 	Ordinal
	Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance commitment • Governance commitment 	Ordinal
Innovation capability	Adoption New Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willingness to adopt • Skill Transforming 	Ordinal
	Employee Open-Mindedness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thinking out of the box • Evaluating all options 	Ordinal
External stakeholder interest	Reciprocity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jointness • Affordability 	Ordinal
	Trust building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparent • Accessibility 	Ordinal

Sample

The sampling technique used in this study was through a census to provide equal opportunities to all BPJS Kesehatan branches as the research population as well as the sample. BPJS Kesehatan has deputy regional offices which are divided into 13 regions consisting of 126 branch offices (one branch office is administrative) and 388 district/city offices.

Data collection

Data collection in this study was carried out by means of in-depth interviews and filling out questionnaires with open and closed questions. This research begins with in-depth interviews with managers at the minimum level as an effort to explore problems in the region. The data were analyzed using a qualitative approach with Nvivo software as a coding tool. Quantitative data retrieval is done through filling out questionnaires. The results were enriched through open-ended questions.

RESULT

Profile of the respondents

Branch offices are spread throughout Indonesia and are regionally divided into 13 regions. Meanwhile, the workload is divided into 3 classes, namely the main branch office (15), class A branch office (28), and class B branch office (60).

Table 1. Profile of Respondents

Description	Indicator	Percentage
Branch office category by class	Main branch office	15
	Branch office type A	27
	Branch office type B	58
Gender	Male	57,03
	Female	42,07
Educational background	Diploma	53,04
	Master	44,07
Experience as branch head	Experienced	69
	Inexperienced	34

Source: Author's own Research, 2021

Measurement model results

The model shows that the construct of Effective Leadership Sustainability (ELS) is measured by 2 dimensions, namely controlling with 2 indicators and self-awareness with 3 indicators. While the construct of Innovation Capability (IC) is measured by 2 dimensions, namely adoption with 2 indicators and open mind with 2 indicators. The External Stakeholder Interest (ESI) construct has 2 dimensions, namely jointness with 2 indicators and trust building with 2 indicators. Finally, the Collaborative Sustainability Performance (CSP) construct is measured with 3 dimensions, namely community with 2 indicators, employee with 2 dimensions and institution with 3 indicators.

Goodness of Fit – Model

In testing the fit of the model (Goodness of Fit – Model), it consists of 3 types of tests including the suitability test of the measurement model (outer model), structural model fit test (inner model) and Evaluation of Goodness of Fit (GoF) – Inner Model.

Measurement Model Fit Test (Outer Model)

Testing the outer model is done by analyzing the results of convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is measured by loading factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) parameters; Construct Reliability is measured by Cronbachs Alpha and Composite Reliability parameters. An indicator is declared valid if it has a loading factor above 0.70 for the intended construct while the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value generated by all constructs must be above > 0.5. And to see the results of construct reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values must be above 0.7 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The following is a test of convergent validity and construct reliability:

Effective Leadership Sustainability (ELS)

Table 1. Validity Test of Effective leadership sustainability Variables

Laten/ Observed Variable		Loading factor	AVE
1st CFA	Controlling		0.785
	ELSa	0.946	
	EL Sb	0.822	
	Self-awareness		0.577
	ELSc	0.847	
	ELSd	0.800	
ELSd	0.712		
Latent	Effective leadership sustainability		0.633

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 1. shows the results of factor loading that there is no factor loading value below 0.7 and the AVE value of the dimensions of controlling and self-awareness and the latent variable of Effective leadership sustainability is above 0.5, which means all indicators on Effective leadership sustainability are valid. And here are the results of the reliability test:

Table 2. Results of Continuous Effective Leadership Reliability Testing (Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability)

Dimension	Reliability		Conclusion
	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	
Controlling	0.744	0.879	Reliable
Self-awareness	0.743	0.801	Reliable
Latent Variable			
Effective leadership sustainability	0.723	0.774	Reliable

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 2 shows that all indicators are valid. And based on the table above, all dimensions formed from the indicators and latent variables are reliable.

Innovation Capability (IC)

Table 3. Test the validity of Innovation Capability

Laten/ Observed Variable	Loading factor	AVE	Conclusion
1st CFA	Adoption		0.726
	IC1a	0.862	
	IC1b	0.903	
	Open mind		0.715
	IC2a	0.872	
	IC2b	0.819	
Latent	Innovation capability	0.589	Valid

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 3 shows the results of the loading factor that there is no loading factor value below 0.7 and the AVE value of the dimensions of adoption and open mind and the latent variable of Innovation Capability is above 0.5 which means that all indicators on Innovation Capability are valid. And here are the results of the reliability test:

Table 4. Results of Innovation Capability Reliability Testing (Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability)

Dimension	Reliability		Conclusion
	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	
Adoption	0.719	0.876	Reliable
Open mind	0.704	0.834	Reliable
Latent Variable			
Innovation capability	0.764	0.851	Reliable

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 4 shows that all indicators are valid. And based on the table, all the dimensions formed from the indicators and the latent variables are reliable.

External Stakeholder Interests (ESI)

Table 5. Validity Test of External Stakeholder Interest Variables

Laten/ Observed Variable	Loading factor	AVE	Conclusion
1st CFA Jointness		0.789	Valid
ES1a	0.701		Valid
ES1b	0.941		Valid
Trust build		0.835	Valid
ES1c	0.901		Valid
ES1d	0.952		Valid
ES1e	0.887		Valid
Latent External Stakeholder Interests		0.627	Valid

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 5 shows the results of the loading factor that there is no loading factor value below 0.7 and the AVE value of the dimensions of jointness and trust build as well as the latent variable of External Stakeholder Interest above 0.5 which means all indicators show valid. And here are the results of the reliability test:

Table 6. Results of External Stakeholder Interest Reliability Testing (Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability)

Dimension	Reliability		Conclusion
	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	
Jointness	0.790	0.813	Reliable
Trust build	0.901	0.938	
Latent Variable			
External stakeholder interest	0.705	0.771	

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 6 shows that all indicators are valid. And based on the table above, all dimensions formed from the indicators and latent variables are reliable.

Collaborative Sustainability Performance (CSP)

Table 7. Validity Test of Collaborative Sustainability Performance Variables

Laten/ Observed Variable	Loading Factor	AVE	Conclusion
1st CFA Comm		0.809	Valid
CSP1a	0.885		Valid
CSP1b	0.913		Valid
Employ		0.636	Valid
CSP2a	0.856		Valid
CSP2b	0.734		Valid
Inst		0.698	Valid
CSP3a	0.711		Valid
CSP3b	0.909		Valid
CSP3c	0.873		Valid
Latent Collaborative Sustainability Performance		0.556	Valid

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 7 shows the results of the loading factor that is not below 0.7 and the AVE value of the dimensions of community, employee, and institution as well as the latent variable of Collaborative Sustainability Performance is above 0.5 which means that all indicators on Collaborative Sustainability Performance are valid. And here are the results of the reliability test:

Table 8. Results of Collaborative Sustainability Performance Reliability Testing (Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability)

Dimension	Reliability		Conclusion
	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	
Comm	0.764	0.894	Reliable
Employ	0.734	0.776	
Inst	0.777	0.873	
Latent Variable			
Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.798	0.853	

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 8 shows that all indicators are valid. And based on the table above, all the dimensions formed from the indicators and the latent variables are reliable

Structural Model Fit Test (Inner Model)

Assessing the inner model to see the relationship between latent constructs by looking at the estimation results of the path parameter coefficients and their level of significance. In the assessment of the inner model by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The following is the R-square value in the construct:

Table 9. R-Square

Dependent variable	R Square
Innovation capability	0.607
Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.814

Source: Researcher's own study (2021)

Table 9 shows that the R-Square value for the innovation capability construct gives a result of 0.607. This means that the construct of innovation capability can be explained by the construct of organizational collaboration culture, Effective leadership sustainability and stakeholder management by 60.7%.

Meanwhile, the R-Square value of the Collaborative Sustainability Performance construct is 0.814. This means that the Collaborative Sustainability Performance construct is explained by organizational collaboration culture, Effective leadership sustainability, stakeholder management, innovation capability and Stakeholder value of 81.4%.

Evaluation of Goodness of Fit (GoF) – Inner Model

To evaluate the GoF – Inner Model, it is done by looking at the values of R-Square (R²), Q-Square (Q²) and GoF. The following is the test of the Inner Model with Q² (predictive relevance):

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R1^2) (1 - R2^2) (1 - R3^2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.607) (1 - 0.412) (1 - 0.814)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0.043$$

$$Q^2 = 0,957$$

From these results obtained Q² (0.957) > 0, indicating that the model has predictive relevance (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The Q² predictive relevance value of 0.957 indicates that the model is strong.

Furthermore, by analyzing the Goodness of Fit (GoF), which is calculated by the square root of the average communality index value with the average R-Square (R²).

$$GoF = \sqrt{Com \times R^2}$$

The Com value is obtained from the average AVE value of 0.68 so that the GoF value can be calculated as follows:

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,68 \times 0,611}$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0,416}$$

$$GoF = 0,645$$

The GoF value of 0.645 indicates that the model in this study is included in the Strong criteria.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING AND DISCUSSION

Manifest Variables Analysis of Latent Variables

To predict the causality relationship between latent variables, this research was carried out through a bootstrapping process.

Effective leadership sustainability Variable

Table 10. Effective leadership sustainability Variable Bootstrapping

Dimension	Indicator	Bootstrapping Result
Controlling		35.181
	ELSa	96.385
	EL Sb	7.857
Self-awareness		21.466
	ELSc	27.995
	ELSd	12.630
	ELSe	7.894

Source: Researcher’s own study (2021)

Table 10 shows that from the Effective leadership sustainability variable, there are 2 dimensions, namely controlling and self-awareness. Of the two dimensions, the strongest form of Effective leadership sustainability variable is the controlling dimension and the last is self-awareness.

For each dimension there are indicators that make up. For the dimension of controlling indicator, the strongest forming dimension is ELSa, followed by EL Sb. Furthermore, the self-awareness dimension is the strongest indicator that forms the dimensions, namely ELSc, next is ELSd, and finally ELSe.

Innovation capability

Table 11. Bootstrapping Innovation Capability Variables

Dimension	Indicator	Bootstrapping Result
Adoption		48.670
	IC1a	23.863
	IC1b	64.313
Open mind		31.589
	IC2a	46.124
	IC2b	22.486

Source: Researcher’s own study (2021)

Table 11 shows that from the innovation capability variable there are 2 dimensions, namely adoption and open mind. Of the two dimensions, the strongest forming the innovation capability variable is the adoption dimension and the last is open mind.

For each dimension there are indicators that make up. For the adoption dimension, the strongest indicator forms the dimensions, namely IC1b, and finally IC1a. Furthermore, the dimensions of the open mind indicator that are the strongest form the dimensions, namely IC2a and finally IC2b.

External stakeholder interest variable

Table 12. Bootstrapping of External Stakeholder Interest Variables

Dimension	Indicator	Bootstrapping Result
jointness		9.611
	ES1a	4.533
	ES1b	10.854
Trust build		6.858
	ES1c	13.538
	ES1d	15.368
	ES1e	11.866

Source: Researcher’s own study (2021)

Table 12 shows that from the variable interest of external stakeholders, there are 2 dimensions including jointness and trust build. Of the two dimensions, the strongest forming the external stakeholder interest variable is the dimension of jointness and the last is trust build.

Each dimension has an indicator that forms. For the jointness dimension, the strongest indicator forming the dimension is ES1b, and finally ES1a. Furthermore, the dimension of trust build indicator which is the strongest forming the dimension is ES1d, then ES1c and finally ES1e.

Collaborative Sustainability Performance Variables

Table 13. Collaborative Sustainability Performance Variable Bootstrapping

Dimension	Indicator	Bootstrapping Result
comm		16.542
	CSP1a	28.007
	CSP1b	52.590
employ		14.572
	CSP2a	21.973
	CSP2b	8.653
Inst		26.733
	CSP3a	12.967
	CSP3b	44.612
	CSP3c	26.354

Source: Researcher’s own study (2021)

Table 13 shows that from the Collaborative Sustainability Performance variables, there are 3 dimensions including community, employee and institution. Of the three dimensions that form the strongest collaboration performance variables, namely the institutional, community and finally employee dimensions.

For each dimension there are indicators that make up. For the community dimension, the strongest indicator forming the dimension is CSP1b, and the last one is CSP1a. Next is the employee dimension, the strongest indicator forming the dimension, namely CSP2a, and finally CSP2b. The last dimension is institution, the strongest indicator forming the dimension is CSP3b, then CSP3c and finally CSP3a.

Hypothesis test

To test the hypothesis using the output path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) provided that if the t statistic value obtained from the table is greater than 1.96 and the p-value <0.05, the hypothesis between the existing variables is accepted. On the other hand, if the value of t statistics is less than 1.96, the p-value > 0.05, then the hypothesis is rejected. Meanwhile, to determine the magnitude of the influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable, it can be seen from the path coefficient value.

Table 14. Path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) - 1

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STERR)	P-Value	Result
Direct Effect						
Innovation capability -> Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.296	0.297	0.095	3.129	0.001	Significant
Effective leadership sustainability -> Innovation capability	0.212	0.201	0.087	2.436	0.008	Significant
Effective leadership sustainability -> Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.136	0.135	0.069	1.982	0.024	Significant
IC*ESI -> Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.246	0.224	0.105	2.350	0.009	Significant
Indirect Effect						

Effective leadership sustainability -> Innovation capability -> Collaborative Sustainability Performance	0.063	0.060	0.034	1.856	0.032	Significant
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Source: Researcher’s own study (2021)

Hypothesis testing is an effort to determine the effect of each hypothesis based on the hypothesis test design by testing the path between variables. Proof is done through the value of t-statistics and path coefficients. The t-statistic value describes the significance of the construct while the path coefficient describes the nature of the relationship between constructs. The results are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Effective leadership sustainability on Innovation Capability

From table 14 (Path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) it is found that the T-statistical value (2.436) > 1.96 and P-Value (0.008) < 0.05, and the original sample value is 0.212 (signed from these results, the hypothesis which states that Effective leadership sustainability has an effect on Innovation Capability is accepted. Effective leadership sustainability has a positive and significant impact on Innovation Capability. The higher Effective leadership sustainability, the greater the Innovation Capability. In other studies, Innovation Capability Companies are indeed different and influenced by many factors with various influencing aspects such as aspects of leadership, individuals, teams, and other supporting components (Saunila et al., 2013).

Hypothesis 2: Effective leadership sustainability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance

From table 14 (Path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) it is found that the T-statistical value (1.982) > 1.96 and P-Value (0.024) < 0.05, and the original sample value is 0.136 (signed from these results, the hypothesis which states that Effective leadership sustainability has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance is accepted. Effective leadership sustainability has a positive and significant impact on Collaborative Sustainability Performance. The higher the Effective leadership sustainability, the more Collaborative Sustainability Performance will be. Conceptually the role sustainable leadership demonstrated through the implementation of effective behavioral principles and a commitment to governance and values/principles in building change that has an impact on achieving the triple bottom line (Ulrich & Smallwood, 2015).

Furthermore, on the indirect effect of Effective leadership sustainability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance through the mediation of Innovation Capability. From table 14 it is found that T-statistic (1.976) > 1.96 and P-Value (0.032) < 0.05, and the original sample value is 0.163 (positive sign). From these results, the hypothesis which states that Effective leadership sustainability has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance through the mediation of Innovation Capabilities is accepted, so in this case the Innovation Capability variable can mediate the effect of Effective leadership sustainability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance. In other studies, collaboration is in dire need of creative leaders, and through innovation brings about changes to the environment and achievement of performance (Hambleton, 2019; Maghsoudi, Pereira & Lara, 2020; Newman-Storen, 2014).

Hypothesis 3: Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance

From table 14 (Path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) it is found that the T-statistical value (3.129) > 1.96 and P-Value (0.001) < 0.05, and the original sample value is 0.296 (signed from these results, the hypothesis which states that Innovation Capability has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance is accepted. Innovation Capability has a positive and significant impact on Collaborative Sustainability Performance. The higher the Innovation Capability, the higher the Collaborative Sustainability Performance.

Cooperation involving “public-private” requires increased innovation. Innovation capability is an “operational capability” that affects collaboration (Chi et al., 2018; Carbonara et al., 2018).

Hypothesis 4: Innovation Capability on Collaborative Sustainability Performance Moderated Interests of External Stakeholders

From table 14 (Path coefficients (Mean, STDEV, T-Values) it is found that the T-statistical value (2.350) > 1.96 and P-Value (0.009) < 0.05, and the original sample value is 0.246 (positive sign). From these results, the hypothesis which states that Innovation Capability has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance moderated by External Stakeholder Interests is accepted.

Innovation is not an easy problem, especially for the healthcare industry. Many parties are involved and have their own justifications. Innovation Capability can only affect collaboration performance when it considers the interests of stakeholders. Thus, the interest of external stakeholders is a concern in innovating (Chi et al., 2018; Keskin et al., 2012; Weber & Khademian, 2008).

Theoretical Implications

Collaboration is an important instrument in achieving sustainable social impact performance. Previous research has shown the important role of collaboration in dealing with complex problems. In this study, collaboration is positioned as an inseparable part of social sustainability. Thus, the outcome indicators that are prepared are also based on social sustainability.

In research on social sustainability, using a sustainable social dimension that has an impact on humanity (well-being) is passive. On the other hand, social sustainability also requires active support for system sustainability (Stephen McKenzie, 2004). The system also requires the sustainability of the controlling institution. In this study there are indicators of institutions as an integral part in building social sustainability. This is also in line with previous research showing indicators of social sustainability including institutional-based indicators (Hale et al., 2019).

The collaboration model (Ansell, 2008) shows the role of institutions in the collaboration process. Meanwhile, in this study, organizational culture is used as an antecedent to collaboration outcomes, namely Collaborative Sustainability Performance. The results of the study show the role that Organizational Collaboration Culture has a direct effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance

Managerial Implications

This study provides managerial implications for institutions at the head office and at branch offices. For leaders at the head office need to develop a culture of organizational collaboration. This has a direct impact on the performance of sustainable collaboration. Organizational culture shows a strong role in an organization, especially in building the involvement of other parties. Human Resources Development as a leader in branch offices needs to be developed based on individual behavior that can encourage innovation capabilities.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the answers to research questions related to research objectives, both those related to scientific interests and problem solving, were in accordance with the results of theoretical studies and testing of research results. Some of the findings of this study include Effective Sustainable Leadership has a direct effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance, and Innovation Capability moderated by External Stakeholder Interests has an effect on Collaborative Sustainability Performance.

This research still needs to be done by involving various parties. The diversity of industries and parties involved can provide a more comprehensive picture, especially with regard to the interests of external stakeholders. Even though many studies have been carried out related to the diversity of interests, needs and interests of stakeholders, every organization and stakeholder needs to get the right formulation because value(s) do not stand alone but are interrelated.

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